

The Effect of COVID-19 Pandemic on the Business Operation of Selected Coffee Shops in Dasmaringas City

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Abstract: The paper discussed the effect of COVID-19 pandemic on the Business Operation of selected Coffee Shops in Dasmaringas City. The researchers conducted the study to the selected coffee shops in Dasmaringas City, Cavite based on their rank on the Tripadvisor review. Researchers used descriptive type of quantitative research design and sampling method to engage participants who are knowledgeable and can in-deftly provide valuable insights and information about the effect of COVID-19 pandemic on the business operation efficiency of the selected coffee shops and surveyed (30) selected participants that was willing to cooperate using google forms. Data collected were analyzed by using statistical methods to have a clear results. The collected data analysis results including the (4) four operational management; Service, Sales, Marketing and Procurement shows the effect of COVID-19 pandemic to the business operation on said businesses.

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3 Lot 7 Mabuhay City Phase 2 Extension Paliparan, COVID-19 - Illness in human that caused by a virus.

Business Operation - A term that used to describe a variety of different activities.

Tripadvisor - It is a travel website that helps customers in terms of travel information, submitting reviews and opinions of travel-related content.

Procurement- It is an act of making purchase or services, usually have an relation to business spending.

1. INTRODUCTION

Coffee shops are considered to be one of the favorite places where people meet to chat, drink coffee, read and socialize. It served as a meeting place where people can relax according to Ferreira, J. (2020) or place used for meetings and hanging out, (Suarez, A.N., Lacay, J.K., Villanueva, V., Velasquez, R.A., Reyes, D.C., Serrano, V., & Borbon, J.C.D., 2017).

When coffee shops became popular in Cavite (Eusebio, M.A., 2015), there was sudden increase in the demand which led to the upturn of Coffee shop businesses. In locations near universities, it became the favorite study hub for students or those who want to have a quiet place to finish whatever work they need to accomplish. Over the years, it has been a favorite hangout for both young and old alike especially those coffee lovers.

As coffee shops draw customers, they also help tourist attractions located on their area, Suarez, et. al., (2017) to be visited as well, thereby contributing to the economy of the province.

Unfortunately, COVID-19 pandemic greatly affected the industry. In order to mitigate the risks of COVID-19, governments issued health protocols and travel restrictions. The government controlled the movement of society by imposing lockdowns, temporary closure of businesses, and health protocols such as social distancing and capacity restriction.

These protocols forced coffee shops and other business establishments to shut down, which left owners with no choice but to reduce their number of employees. However, when restrictions were slowly relaxed and establishments were allowed to open, their operations drastically shifted to take outs, less operating hours, and few products offered, and most of them changed their physical layouts to an online set-up (Dr. Ferreira, J., & Dr. Ferreira, C., 2020), where services are conducted primarily through phone and online applications where customers can connect and order without having to visit the premises.

This mislays their ability to give their customers special experience and showcase the development of its physical location (Strategic Analysis, 2020). Researchers see the need to study the changes in the business operation of hospitality businesses caused by the pandemic in order to bring back the customers to hospitality businesses since people are still uncomfortable going to a restaurant, coffee shops, or even in a hotel because of the fear of getting infected by the virus (Gursoy D. & Chi C. D., 2020).

Overall, the researchers aim to determine how the COVID-19 Pandemic affected the Business Operation of Selected Coffee Shops in Dasmarinas City. In particular, this study seeks to identify the effect of the said pandemic to the business operation of coffee shops in terms of customer satisfaction and its attributes such as atmosphere, employee attitudes, IT service and coffee quality (Lee WS., Moon J., & Song M., 2018) including the implications of the findings on the business operation of coffee shops amid pandemic.

Research Paradigm

Research Paradigm will apply Input, Process, and Output to carry out the investigations. It determines the effect of variables to each other. Input has all the questions that should be answered. Process is the method that use to gather all the answers from the input. Lastly, the output is the outcome and recommendation after processing the input (Dr. Rosales, R., 2020).

The first box contains the Part I of the research instrument consists of demographic profiles of the participants such as name, age, location, occupation and company. It also includes the objectives and title of the research under investigation. Part II of the research instrument is the guided questions. It is a series of questions to be read and answered in-deftly. The questions aim to answer the effects of the pandemic on the business operation efficiency in the selected coffee shops in Dasmarinas, Cavite.

The second box contains the process on how the researchers will do the data gathering which is the questionnaires via google forms and statistical analysis.

The third box is the output that shows the implications of the findings on the business operation efficiency of coffee shop amid pandemic including the recommendations of the researchers.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Statement of the Problem

The focus of this study is to determine the effect of COVID-19 pandemic on the business operation of selected coffee shops in Dasmariñas City, Cavite by determining the changes emerged, and its implications on the business operation of coffee shops. Through identifying how the COVID-19 affected the coffee shops, the researchers aim to contribute to the development of the food and beverage industry.

Specifically, it aimed that this research would provide answers to questions:

1. What is the profile of the coffee shops in terms of?
 - a. Years of operation
 - b. Location
 - c. Ratings
2. How do the respondents assess the effect of the pandemic to their business operation in terms of :
 - a. Service
 - b. Sales
 - c. Marketing
 - d. Procurement
3. Is there any significant relationship between the profile of the coffee shops and the effect of pandemic to their business operation?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This section presents the literature and studies to discuss the related major aspects of the study: Coffee shops and its business operation and how did COVID-19 pandemic change its way of operation, and the challenges coffee shops faced amid pandemic.

Service

The objective of a customer service is to create loyalty between the customers and the company (Gupta, C., 2021). Thus, atmosphere and employee attitudes are essential to make the customers feel comfortable with the company that they engage with.

The atmosphere will not only attract and catch customers, but it also urges people to spend money at a specific shop. Hence, COVID-19 influence the atmosphere of coffee shops since diners should be limited. It creates a more engaging online atmosphere through an app or digital loyalty program which encourage more customers to keep coming back to the online store. It may not be the traditional coffee shops' atmosphere but it still connects the brand and the customers closely to each other's (The Importance of Coffee Shop Atmospheric, 2021). One of the examples of this is Starbucks which already doing this even before the pandemic came but it expands and engages more customers since all the restrictions caused by the pandemic became mandatory (Kelso, A., 2020)

On the other hand, employee attitudes are included in the service quality of a coffee shop. Positive attitude of an employee impacts the satisfaction of customers (Lee, Moon, and Song., 2018). Meanwhile, the rising COVID-19 positive cases negatively influence employee attitudes. As an example, job insecurity will begin once the employee who see low future in the organizations that they currently belong. Knowing that it is not also easy to find another job this time of crisis, employees do not have choice but to stay.

Another thing is when the employees were concerned how risky their works are and started finding justification on being expose to such risks, it decreases their work motivation and satisfaction (Bajrami,D.D., Terzić, A., Petrovićab M.D., Radovanović, M., Tretiakova, T.N., Hadoud, A., 2021).

Sales & Marketing

Sales together with the promotions, advertising, & public relations are under the umbrella of marketing. It focuses to contact customers to gain income and updates the marketing department on the customers comments. While, the marketing department tells the sales staff what tools is will use and what to emphasize (Milano, S., 2019). Moreover, IT service contributes an important role in the sales and marketing departments to operate especially this pandemic.

Technologies are involved in order to reduce the effect of the pandemic. The innovation performance, brand awareness, and the reduction of safety risks were all boosted through the enhancement of information and communication technologies (Lau, A., 2020). Coffee shops should make use of all available materials including social media to engage with their customers and provide contemporary experience. As an example, Starbucks Coffee is well known for its diversified products and strong brand perception. However, Starbucks should reorganize its promotional strategy and utilize social media to adapt to the new normal (Lombardi, et. al., 2021). Additionally, coffee shops are suggested to utilize social media channels to convey information and engage with its customers. Developing its digital presence can help with its operation and promotions (Al-Fadly, A., 2020). According to Joseph, O., et. al. (2020), the development of social media opened a path for businesses amid the pandemic. With the absence of a physical aspect in providing service, digital marketing and promotions is one of the most optimal approaches businesses can do. They should make use of the internet to engage with its customers and resume its operation.

Digital marketing refers to the development of digital presence for businesses that focus on promotion. It assesses owners to offer goods or services online while minimizing its cost for promotions. It is vital for coffee shop owners to remember that customers nowadays prefer seeing updated and well-presented contents and it influences their buying behavior. Coffee shop owners can also offer service incentive programs such as discounted products and delivery charges. Also, customers also consider reviews and comments of other customers in their decision rather than just simply relying on the contents of the business. Digital marketing is now starting to highlight amid pandemic. Utilizing social media platforms allows businesses to not only promote their brand with their online presence but most importantly, engage with its customers as well (Lopez, R., 2020). Digital marketing is vital during the pandemic. Although the sales were not as same as it was before, utilizing digital marketing can greatly help businesses to produce sales and recover financially (Joseph, et. al., 2020).

Procurement

Allowing a company to obtain the goods and services they require at the exact time is a productive procurement. It is impossible for the company to succeed in the operation efficiently without the help of the procurement department (Sharkey, S. & CFP Herman, M., 2021). However, the crisis brought by the COVID-19 challenged this department in terms of coffee quality and the workers.

Good quality coffee has a lot of factors especially during the procedure but here are the basic factors: secured packaging, strong aroma that smells fresh, and its taste which is based on the roast time, method, and freshness of a coffee (What Is Good Quality Coffee? 2022). However, Kuswara & Pipinsukandi (2020) claimed that the procedure for qualification in coffee shops was affected during the pandemic. Coffee shop owners are hiring managers tend to give importance to medical tests rather than focusing on the skills requirements to pass the qualification. This resulted on coffee shops to hire incompetent workers. The worker's wages were deeply affected by the pandemic as well. The money they receive is lower than its regular rate. A decrease in employment regarding coffee shops, especially Baristas, occurred due to the threat of COVID-19 pandemic and working on site is heavily unsupported. Moreover, government regulations regarding operation hours and limited capacity led to the closure of some coffee shops. COVID-19.

3. METHODOLOGY

This section provides details on how the researchers will conduct the research. This includes, research design, locale, instruments and data gathering procedures, the participants of the study, and the data treatment analysis.

Research Design

Quantitative research will be utilized in this study. This design aims to collect data that can be transfigured to numbers (Sheard, J., 2010). Quantitative Research Design is the use of numerical tools in fairly, methodical, and actual research of noticeable occurrence (Tamayo, K. 2020). This research seeks to answer the effect of the pandemic that affected the business operation efficiency of Coffee Shops. In this study, a quantitative data collection method will be used wherein the participants will answer questions to explore their views, experience, and beliefs regarding the effects of COVID-19 Pandemic on the business efficiency of Coffee Shops.

Research Locale

This study will be conducted on five (5) selected coffee shops in Dasmarinas City, Cavite based on their rank on the Tripadvisor reviews. According to Tripadvisor, their rankings were based on popularity index such as: quality, date, and quantity of reviews that the establishment received from users.

Participants of the Study and Research Sampling

The participants of this study will be the coffee shops business owners from the selected coffee shops in Dasmarinas, Cavite. Purposive sampling will be used in this research study where the researchers purposely select participants based on the qualifying criteria of famous coffee shops located in Dasmarinas, Cavite, coffee shops that were established even before the pandemic, and were affected by the pandemic. A recommended sample size of not less than 30 participants are required in conducting quantitative research (Delice, A., 2010). The researchers will utilize this sampling method to engage participants who are knowledgeable and can in-deftly provide valuable insights and information about the effect of COVID-19 pandemic on the business operation efficiency of the selected coffee shops.

Research Instrument & Data Gathering Procedures

The researchers will be distributing questionnaires among the participants to gather data for the study. Researchers will be using Google forms to set guided questions where participants will answer accordingly. The responses will be about their opinions, perspectives, experiences, and some company information such as years of operations, location, and ratings.

Part I of the research instrument consists of demographic profiles of the participants. It also includes the objectives and title of the research under investigation. Part II of the research instrument is the guided questions. It is a series of questions to be read and answered in-depthly. The questions aim to answer the effects of the pandemic on the business operation efficiency in the selected coffee shops in Dasmarinas, Cavite.

The set of guided questions will be distributed to the twenty individuals in selected coffee shops in Dasmarinas City. The researchers will conduct surveys through google forms to each of the respondents and the participants will be expected to give their responses and feedback in order for the researchers to gather valuable data. In terms of ethical considerations, to ensure that the researchers and the respondent will not have any misunderstanding, conflicts and concerns in their response, the researchers will make sure that the response of the respondents will be confidential and will only be used as data for the research. The results will be interpreted using descriptive analysis to give an in-depth analysis of the responses.

Data Treatment and Analysis

The quantitative data will be obtained through a survey among the participants in selected coffee shops in Dasmarinas, Cavite. A Statistical Data Analysis will be utilized in this research. The primary tool to analyze data is Microsoft Excel. It helps quantitative research design record, organize, and manage data to create richer insights and findings backed by rigorous evidence (Mr. Diliman’s Tech Channel, 2019).

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this part of the study, researchers need to interpret the result of the survey answered by the respondents.

1. What is the profile of the coffee shops in terms of?

1.1 Years of operation;

Years of operation	Frequency	Percent
0 year – 4 years	26	87%
5 years - and above	4	13%
Total	30	100%

Table 1.1 Years of Operation

According to the table above, out of 30 respondents, the majority of coffee shops have been in business for 0-4 years, amounting to 26 coffee shops (87%), while 4 coffee shops (13%), have been in business for 5 years or more.

In his study, Abi Adeleke (2020) found that successful coffee shops that have been in business for more than 5 years have been able to avoid bankruptcy by using good marketing strategies such as product advertising, high quality products, and competitive pricing. However, if you are still a new business owner, there are many things to learn that will help your company grow quickly.1.2 Location;

1.2 Location;

Location	Frequency	Percent
Salawag	10	33%
Paliparan	9	30%
Salitran	11	37%
Total	30	100%

Table 1.2 Location

As shown in the table above, 10 of the 30 respondents (33%) are Salawag residents. There are also 9 respondents from Paliparan, accounting for 30% of the total. Finally, 11 of the 30 respondents are Salitran residents, accounting for 37% of the total.

Jones Lang (2022) states that choosing where should locate a business has always been significant. Location is extremely important in attracting and retaining customers and staffs. A company's ultimate performance can be significantly boosted by wise location decisions. Based on current trends, location planning allows you to future-proof your operations.

1.3 Ratings via Facebook review

Ratings via Facebook review	Frequency	Percent
5 stars	18	60%
4 stars	8	27%
3 stars	2	7%
2 stars	1	3%
1 star	1	3%
Total	30	100.00%

Table 1.3 Ratings via Facebook Review

According to the table, 18 of the 30 coffee shops received 5 stars, accounting for 60% of the total. There are also 8 coffee shops that have received four-star ratings. There are two coffee shops with two stars. Finally, two coffee shops received two and one star ratings, representing 3% of the 30 respondents.

According to Atanu Shaw (2018), according to his study, 85% of customers rely on online reviews more than suggestions from friends and family. Almost 70% of customers are more likely to use a local business with excellent reviews, while 40% avoid local businesses with poor reviews. Facebook reviews are important in today's generation since most people use Facebook to seek coffee shops with high-quality products and services. They can determine whether the shop is decent or not by using Facebook reviews.

2. How do the respondents assess the effect of the pandemic to their business operation in terms of :

2.1 Service;

Service	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Q1.1 They are responsive to the demand of the customers.	3.57	Major
Q1.2 Regarding the clients' concerns, the employees ae polite.	3.57	Major
Q1.3 They are willing to listen to the complaints of the customers.	3.57	Major
Q1.4 They are knowledgeable about the products they offer.	3.57	Major
Overall Perception on Service	3.57	Major

Table 2.1 Service

As shown in the table above, all of the questions with a verbal interpretation of Major have a mean of 3.57. The average mean of these questions under Service is 3.57, with Major as the overall verbal interpretation. In this time of pandemic, being responsive, polite, willing to listen to complaints, and knowledgeable about the products has a major effect on assessing business.

2.2 Sales and Marketing;

Sales and Marketing	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Q2.1 They create online advertisements that are relevant to the current issue which is COVID - 19 pandemic.	3.47	Major
Q2.2 Provides free delivery services when the minimum requirement is met.	3.40	Major
Q2.3 The customers receive promos and coupons for discounts when purchasing a product.	3.30	Major
Q2.4 They provide quality customer service. (minimum requirements)	3.73	Major
Overall Perception on Sales and Marketing	3.48	Major

Table 2.2 Sales and Marketing

According to the table above, question 2.4 had the highest mean of 3.73. Question 2.1 got a mean of 3.47. The 2.2 question gained a mean of 3.40, while question 3 obtained a mean of 3.30. With an average mean of 3.48, all four questions above were given a verbal interpretation of Major. Creating pandemic-related advertisements, able to offer free delivery, offering promotions and coupons, and providing quality customer service all have a significant effect on a business' assessment.

2.3 Coffee shops Procurement

Coffee shops Procurement	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Q3.1 They offer understandable current pricing that most customers can afford.	3.57	Major
Q3.2 The products are packaged in a safe and secure manner.	3.80	Major
Q3.3 They provide high quality goods to sell.	3.67	Major
Q3.4 The business maintains an ordered inventory and records, which will help them have a good sales flow.	3.80	Major
Overall Perception on Coffee shops Procurement	3.71	Major

Table 2.3 Coffee shops Procurement

According to Table 2.3, questions 3.2 and 3.4 had the highest mean of 3.80, followed by question 3.3, which had a mean of 3.67. Finally, question 3.1 has a mean of 3.57. All of the questions listed above provide a verbal interpretation of Major. The average mean of these questions is 3.71, which corresponds to Major's verbal interpretation. Offering understandable pricing, safe and secure packaging, high quality goods to sell, and keeping an ordered inventory and records all have a major effect on assessing a business.

3. Is there any significant relationship between the profile of the coffee shops and the effect of pandemic to their business operation?

Service	Chi-Square Value	p-Value	Interpretation
Years of operation	4.05	0.26	Not Significant
Location	5.07	0.53	Not Significant
Ratings via Facebook review	26.50	0.009	Significant
Overall Perception	11.87	0.27	Not Significant

Table 3. Service

Based on the table shown above, when it comes to years of operation and location, there is no significant relationship to the service of a business. Years of operation contain 4.05 of chi-square value and a P-value of 0.26, while location consists of 5.07 of chi-square value and 0.53 of P-value.

Meanwhile, ratings via Facebook review contains a chi-square value of 26.50 and a P-value of 0.009. Which means that it has significant relationship to service. Overall, it contains 11.87 of chi-square value and a P-value of 0.27. With that, the overall interpretation is that the profile of the coffee shops has no significant relationship to the service. The null hypothesis of no significant relationship was not rejected.

Sales and Marketing	Chi-Square Value	p-Value	Interpretation
Years of operation	0.58	0.90	Not Significant
Location	8.12	0.23	Not Significant
Ratings via Facebook review	10.65	0.56	Not Significant
Overall Perception	6.45	0.56	Not Significant

Table 4. Sales and Marketing

As per the table above, there is no significant relationship between the profile of coffee shops and Sales and Marketing. Years of operation gained 0.58 of chi-square value and a p-value of 0.90, location contains 8.12 of chi-square value and 0.23 p-value. Lastly, ratings via facebook review got 10.65 of chi-square value and a p-value of 0.56.

All of these profile of coffee shops contains an interpretation of not significant amounting to a chi-square value of 6.45 and a p-value of 0.56. Meaning, there is no significant relationship between profile of coffee shops and sales and marketing. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship was not rejected.

Coffee shop Procurement	Chi-Square Value	p-Value	Interpretation
Years of operation	1.05	0.79	Not Significant
Location	4.73	0.58	Not Significant
Ratings via Facebook review	8.33	0.76	Not Significant
Overall Perception	4.70	0.71	Not Significant

Table 5. Coffee shop Procurement

As the table shown above, there is no significant relationship between the profile of coffee shops and Coffee shop procurement. Years of operation contains a chi-square value of 1.05 and a p-value of 0.79. Location has a 4.73 of chi-square value and a p-value of 0.58. Lastly, ratings via facebook review gained a chi-square value of 8.33 and a p-value of 0.71.

All of these profile of coffee shops contains an interpretation of not significant amounting to a chi-square value of 4.70 and a p-value of 0.71. Meaning, there is no significant relationship between profile of coffee shops and coffee shop procurement. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship was not rejected.

5. CONCLUSION

The researchers had come up with a conclusions and discussed about the effect of COVID-19 pandemic on the Business Operation of selected Coffee Shops in Dasmarinas City. The researchers gathered data and information to increase the knowledge about how operations management works during pandemic on the selected coffee shops around Dasmarinas City, Cavite.

Based on the findings above;

Profile of the coffee shops in terms of;

- Years of Operations
- Locations
- Ratings

As shown in the result of the survey which has a total of (30) thirty respondents, as of the profile of coffee shops in terms of; Years of operations, Locations and Ratings. The years of operations showed that the highest percentage was at the 0-4 years of operation, researchers concluded that out of 30 participants 26 respondents voted for 0-4 years in terms of their business years of operations. On the Location the majority of the respondents that took the survey voted for "Salitran" in Dasmarinas City with a total of 11 participants equivalent to 37% in total, and for the ratings of selected Coffee shops majority voted for "5 stars" with a total of 18 participants equivalent to 60% which represent a good performance about of their business.

The study is all about the effect of COVID-19 Pandemic on the Business Operation of Selected Coffee Shops in Dasmarinas City, researchers used (4) four important variables that is under of operational management which are; Service, Sales, Marketing and Procurement, these variables helps researchers to identify the effect of the said virus (COVID-19) on the business operation of selected coffee shops. In conclusion it is to know how the (4) four Operational Management works

on this kind of establishments. The study showed how effective the variables that researchers used to gathered data, with a 0-4 years of business operations and a 60% of high rating businesses of the selected Coffee Shops around Dasmariñas City, which means it still reflects a good image for this kind of business operation during pandemic. Moreover, participants proved that majority of them are representing a successful and good Operational Management of selected Coffee Shops around Dasma City in terms of a data that researchers have been gathered. It shows clear statement that can help for a business to attract more customers.

Furthermore, based on the findings of the study, using some statistical methods researchers conclude that there is no significant relationship between the profile of coffee shops and their assessment of the effect of pandemic in business operation in terms of; Service, Sales, Marketing and Procurement. The findings that have been gather showed null with their overall perceptions on this study; The Effect of COVID-19 Pandemic on the Business Operation of Selected Coffee Shops in Dasmariñas City.

6. RECOMMENDATION

For the recommendation of the study, researchers will discuss the possible suggestions to improve this study; “The Effect of COVID-19 Pandemic on the Business Operation of Selected Coffee Shops in Dasmariñas City”

- Choosing a right place to establish a micro-businesses, means understanding and choosing right qualities for your business.
- Businesses during pandemic allows business owners to think and overcome the dilemma. It is a good idea for business owners to take advantage of the current situation by taking orders online and deliver it on customers doorsteps.
- Considering the Pandemic in this situation ordering online was popular nowadays. In promoting their product the use of social media will be a good help for the business at marketing and sales strategies by advertising online.

In addition, future studies relating to this study can be conducted, it can be the correlation study of consumers behavior and marketing strategies or other influencing factors that affects customers satisfaction. Researchers believe that tis study can provide enough information for future researchers who will conduct study relating to the effect of COVID-19 Pandemic on the Business Operation of Selected Coffee Shops in Dasmariñas City.

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